

The Role Of High Schools For The Provision Of Educational Services In Rural And Urban Areas Of Goa

Ms. Suharsha Suresh Sawant¹ & Prof. (Dr.) Prabir Kumar Rath²

¹M A Dissertation Student,

²Professor and HoD, PG Department of Geography, Govt. College, Khandola-Goa, 403107.

Corresponding Author – Ms. Suharsha Suresh Sawant

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Abstract:

Education is very important for the development of students and society all over the world. Educational services are not equally distributed between rural and urban areas. Provision of educational services refers to the infrastructure, learning resources and technology, quality of teaching and teaching methods, co-curricular activities and overall development etc. A case study of two high schools, one which is located in rural area of Tiswadi taluka, namely Shri Saraswati High school in ST. Estevam village and the other in urban area of Ponda taluka, e.g. A. J. De Almeida high school, Ponda.

The main objective of this study is to analyze and compare students' perception towards the provision of educational services in rural and urban areas. To identify students' accessibility and location, school infrastructure, Learning resources, Quality of teaching, different teaching methods, co-curricular and overall development.

Both primary as well as secondary data were used, Students data has been directly collected from questionnaire and some information from the school documents. Data has been analyzed by representing in the form of bar graphs, pie-charts, etc., and also the application of software were used such as QGIS for mapping.

The findings of the study shows majority of the rural and urban students find documentaries and 3D models as effective teaching aids whereas Urban school have good infrastructure facilities compared to the rural school making learning more effective than rural school. Policymakers should adopt some modern teaching methods and techniques from urban school to maintain the balance and fill in the gap among the school in rural areas.

Keywords: Education, Development, Rural, Urban

Introduction:

Educational institutions play a very important role where each individual perceive and understand the world around them. Within the context of Tiswadi and Ponda taluka which is located in Goa it has diverse geographical features, rich in nature and cultural heritage. The provision of educational services play a significant role in ensuring equitable access to education across different geographical region. But the educational services are not equally distributed in rural and urban areas of Goa.

Review of Literature:

In this study by Ghafoor, Awan, and Zia (2015) carried out a “comparative study of public and private schools in District Vehari, Pakistan,” to understand why parents prefer private schools and how educational quality differs between the two systems. The study focused on aspects such as teacher quality, teaching practices, curriculum, school facilities, and the overall learning environment. Information was gathered through questionnaires from students, teachers, school heads, and parents. The study found that public

schools faced problems like weak infrastructure, overcrowded classrooms, and reduced public confidence, even though education was free. On the other hand, private schools showed better academic outcomes and facilities but were not easily affordable for economically weaker families. The study was limited in scope as it covered only one district and one academic year, suggesting the need for wider comparative research.

In this study by Stern (1994), in the report “The Condition of Education in Rural Schools”, examined the status of rural education in the United States. The study highlighted that rural schools play a vital role in educating a large population but face challenges such as limited funding, shortage of qualified teachers, poor infrastructure, and lack of modern facilities. It also noted that students in rural areas often have fewer academic opportunities and limited access to advanced courses compared to urban students. However, rural schools showed strengths like smaller class sizes, closer teacher student relationships, and strong community involvement. The study emphasized the need for better policies, increased funding, and improved infrastructure to reduce educational inequalities and enhance the quality of rural education.

In this study by Singh, Singh, and Singh (2012) studied “Education system and academic satisfaction: A study on rural and urban students of traditional and open education systems in India”. The study aimed to compare satisfaction levels and identify strengths and weaknesses of both systems from the students’ perspective. Data were collected using structured questionnaires and analyzed using statistical methods. The findings showed that students in traditional education reported higher academic satisfaction due to better classroom interaction, peer support, and teacher contact. In contrast, students in the open education system valued flexibility and

accessibility but experienced lower satisfaction because of limited interaction and institutional support.

In this study by Wood (2023), in the study “A Review on Education Differences in Urban and Rural Areas,” examined the main reasons for educational disparities between urban and rural regions. The review highlighted that urban areas generally have better educational infrastructure, trained teachers, libraries, and learning facilities, while rural areas face limited resources and poor facilities.

In this study by Popescu et al. (2022), in their study titled “Gaps in the Education Level Between Rural and Urban Areas in the European Union,” analyzed the educational differences between rural and urban regions across EU member states using Eurostat secondary data for the year 2021. Descriptive statistical analysis and percentage comparisons with EU averages were used, without any primary data collection. The findings revealed that rural areas, on average, show lower levels of educational attainment and higher early school leaving rates compared to urban areas, with countries like Slovakia and Romania having a high rural population. The study emphasized the need for better rural education infrastructure, trained teachers, modern curriculum, and policy interventions. However, it also pointed out that while policies are discussed, their actual implementation and impact are not evaluated, indicating a research gap for field-based and region-specific studies.

Research Gap:

Many studies talked about differences between rural and urban school, but very few studies compared with specific schools from different state or district. There is limited research on qualitative aspects of education such as student perceptions towards education. In most of the rural school don’t have clear up to date

information about problems such as lack of resources, lack of trained teachers etc. There is lack of studies on different teaching methods to make teaching effective.

Research Question:

What is the quality of educational services provided by institutions across rural and urban areas of Goa? How does this quality differ between rural and urban high schools?

Objectives:

1. To examine students' perception of the availability of educational services in rural and urban schools.
2. To compare students' views on the quality of teaching, school facilities, and learning resources in rural and urban areas.
3. To understand students' satisfaction with academic support and school environment.
4. To identify gaps and inequalities in educational services as experienced by students.

Study area:

The present study is included in two selected areas of Goa, one representing an urban region (Ponda) and the other a rural region (St. Estevam). Ponda is one of the major urban centers in the state of Goa and is located in North Goa District. The town has a high population density and a large number of educational institutions. St. Estevam, also known as Jua, is a rural village located in Tiswadi taluka in North Goa District. The selected rural high school in St. Estevam mainly provide education to students from the village and nearby rural settlements.

Fig. 1: Study Area Map of Tiswadi and Ponda Taluka in Goa

Source: Prepared by the authors using QGIS based on SoI Map of India

Methodology:

The present study adopted a survey-based methodology to understand students' perspectives on educational services. Data were collected through a student survey conducted among 80 students, including 40 students from rural areas and 40 students from urban areas. The collected data were carefully organized and analyzed using application software such as QGIS and other basic tools. To make the findings clear and easy to understand, the data were presented in visual forms such as bar graphs, multiple bar graphs, and pie charts. This visual representation helped in comparing rural and urban responses effectively and in interpreting the results in a simple and systematic manner.

Discussion and Findings:

Residential Background of students in Rural and Urban Schools:

The residential background of students plays an important role in understanding access to educational services. The residential background of the students has been shown in Fig. 2.1 and 2.2. In rural school, majority of the students

(90%) came from rural areas and very few (10%) came from urban areas. On the other hand, in urban school majority of the students (73%) came from the urban areas and only 27% students came from rural areas. This suggests that urban school attract not only student from urban areas but also students from surrounding rural areas due to better infrastructure facilities, quality of teaching and availability of competitive facilities.

Fig. 2.1: Residence of students from Rural school

Fig. 2.2: Residence of students from Urban school

Source: Field Survey by Researcher, 2026

Mode of Transportation Used by Students in Rural and Urban Areas:

The mode of transportation used by the students to reach their schools have been shown in Fig.3.1 and 3.2. In rural school, majority of the students depended on school transport followed by private transport and very few students used public transport. In contrast, students from urban school, majority of the students used private transport while some students came by walking and few students used public transport. This shows that students used less frequently school

transport in urban school limited to lower classes but in rural areas school transport was used by all the students. This shows that rural students were more dependent on school transport because of lack of frequent transport facilities, improper road facilities and poor economic condition while urban students had multiple transport facilities.

Fig. 3. 1: Students from the Rural school

Fig. 3.2: Students from the Urban school
Source: Field Survey by Researcher, 2026

Travel Time Required by students to Reach school:

A comparison of travel time taken by students studying in two schools of rural and urban areas has been represented in Fig.4. In the case of A. J. De Almeida high school in urban area, most of the students reached to the school within 10 minutes showing the school is located close to the students’ residence through nearby roads and transport facilities. 20 students took 20 to 30 minutes, while no one took more than 1 hour to reach the school. On the other hand,

students of Shri Saraswati high school in rural area showed different travel time. A large number of students took 20 to 30 minutes to reach the school. Some students required only 10 minutes and very few students took more than one hour to reach to the school. Overall, the difference in travel time highlights the spread of students at different locations and the mode of transport facilities.

Fig. 4: Students from Rural and Urban schools
Source: Field Survey by Researcher, 2026

Conditions of School Buildings and Classrooms in Rural and Urban Areas:

The condition of school buildings and classrooms is an important factor that influences the learning environment of students. This Fig.5 show based on the students opinions on the condition of school buildings and classrooms in rural and urban areas it is categorized in the form of Very good, Good, Moderate and Poor. In urban areas most of the students rated very good infrastructure and classroom conditions and some students rated good infrastructure and classroom conditions. This indicates that urban schools generally have better facilities, proper maintenance and improved classroom conditions which support effective teaching and learning. In contrast in rural areas a large number of students rated the moderate conditions of infrastructure and classroom conditions and few students rated to the poor. This shows rural school face challenges related to infrastructure such as building, insufficient classroom and lack of basic

facilities. Overall comparison highlights a huge gap between rural and urban school. Urban school gets more benefits from better fundings, political support, administrative or management support, while rural school lack behind due to limited resources. Improving school buildings and classroom conditions in rural areas is essential to provide qual learning opportunities and enhance the quality of education.

Fig. 5: School building and classroom condition in rural and urban schools
Source: Field Survey by Researcher, 2026

Students' perception of Most effective teaching aids for learning in rural and urban school:

Teaching aids play an important role in making the learning more effective and interesting. It helps the students to understand difficult concepts through visual and practical methods rather than theoretical explanation. This fig.6 represents the students' opinions on the most effective teaching aids for learning in rural school and urban school. In rural school 14 students rated to the documentaries as the most effective teaching aids. 12 students were preferred of experiential learning in rural settings. 3D models were considered helpful by some students while other 5 students received other teaching aids make them more effective. This suggests that audio-visual content helps rural students better understand the topic by connecting classroom learning with real world examples. In contrast urban students 17 students preferred 3D models as most effective teaching aids. Documentaries and field trips were equally preferred by 7

students these methods show still supportive role in learning. Other teaching aids also received a moderate response from the students. Overall, it highlights a clear difference in teaching between rural and urban areas. Rural students get more benefits from documentaries and field trips which help them visualize concepts beyond textbooks. Urban students preferred 3D models due to availability of technological resources and hands on learning tools.

Fig. 6: Most effective teaching aids for learning
 Source: Field Survey by Researcher, 2026

Frequency of use of modern technology by teachers in rural and urban schools:

Modern technology has become an important part of the teaching learning process. Modern technology such as smart boards, projectors, computers, and digital presentations helps the teachers to explain concepts more clearly and make lessons more interactive and effective. This fig.7 shows how often teachers use modern technology in rural and urban schools, based on student responses. It is categorized into three such as regularly, sometime and never. In rural schools 32 students rated that teachers sometimes use modern technology. This suggests that although technological tools are available, they are not used regularly in classroom teaching. Only 4 students rated that teachers regularly use technology that indicate limited integration of digital tools in daily lessons. Additionally, 4 students reported that teachers never use modern

technology may be due to lack of insufficient training or lack internet facilities. In contrast urban school similar response of students has been observed with large number of 29 students rated that teachers sometimes use modern technology, 8 students rated teacher use regular modern technology and only 3 students mentioned that technology is never used. The difference between in rural and urban schools highlights unequal access to resources, training and infrastructure.

Fig. 7: Frequency of use of modern technology by teachers
 Source: Field Survey by Researcher, 2026

Teaching methods that help in building students’ interest in learning in rural and urban schools:

Teaching methods play a very important role in developing students interest towards learning. In this Fig.8 represents different teaching methods include such as lecture method, project method, effective technology-based tools and field trips or practical works. In rural school 21 students are more interested to learn through field work and practical work by experiencing nature, followed by 12 students are interested to learn through group activity by interacting with each other in project method. Followed by moderately 6 students rated to effective technology-based tool and only 1 student interested to learn through lecture method. In contrast urban school students showed a different pattern. Effective technology-based tools 13

students rated as the most helpful to build interest and it make interactive classroom. And also 13 students rated as field trips or practical works are important it helps to learn from experimental and practical works.

Fig. 8: Teaching method which helps to build interest in learning

Source: Field Survey by Researcher, 2006

Teacher's encouragement strategies for promoting classroom discussion in rural and urban schools:

Classroom discussion is an important part of the teaching learning process as it helps the students to express their ideas and to develop confidence. Teachers use different encouragement strategies such as encourage everyone to talk, use of group activity, providing individual attention and encouragement to perform which helps to promote active participation among students. This Fig.9 it highlights the students' responses regarding various encouragement methods used by teacher in rural and urban school. In rural school the most common encouragement strategy 24 students reported by students is use group activity for participation which help to interact with each other. 10 students reported teacher encourage everyone talk. Encouraging everyone to talk and use group activity for participation both are widely used. Urban students also reported relatively higher levels of individual attention and encouragement to perform are relatively higher than the rural school.

Fig. 9: Teaching method which helps to build interest in learning

Source: Field Survey by Researcher, 2026

Conclusion:

The present study analysed the provision of educational services in rural and urban areas of Goa from the students' perspective. The findings reveal that accessibility to transport, travel time, quality of school infrastructure, classroom environment, laboratory facilities, availability of internet services, and teaching-learning practices significantly influence students' educational experiences. Although educational facilities are available in both rural and urban schools, variations in quality and adequacy are evident. These differences contribute to unequal learning opportunities among students. The study concludes that improving infrastructural facilities, digital access, and learner-centred teaching methods is essential to enhance the effectiveness and equity of educational services in both rural and urban areas of Goa.

Recommendations:

Better road connectivity is required, as many students commute from outside locations. School infrastructure should be well maintained and designed to be student-friendly, creating an environment that encourages enjoyment in learning. Teachers should incorporate modern technology and teaching aids to make classroom instruction more interactive and engaging.

Additionally, educational resources in rural schools should be made comparable to those available in urban schools in order to ensure equity and balanced development across all schools.

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